

STRATEGY FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SPECIAL EMPLOYMENT EXCHANGE POLICIES FOR JOB PLACEMENT AT THE OFFICE OF MANPOWER AND TRANSMIGRATION OF SERANG REGENCY

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Abstract

This research is based on the phenomenon of the high unemployment rate in Indonesia, especially the educated unemployment rate (TPT) among graduates of Vocational High Schools from now on known as SMK in Serang Regency. This is due to the low absorption of vocational graduates by industry and the world of work, while vocational education aims to create a workforce that is ready to be used by industry. The purpose of this study is to describe how the implementation of the Special Job Exchange policy, from now on known as BKK in job placement at Vocational High Schools, to find out what aspects play a role in the implementation of the BKK policy for job placements at Vocational High Schools and to formulate strategies for implementing BKK policies in placements. Work in an ideal and effective Vocational High School. The method used in this study is a descriptive research method with a mixed-method approach with concurrent embedded strategies. Meanwhile, to formulate the policy strategy, the researcher uses a SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) analysis. Analysis of the problem will be studied using the theory of policy implementation proposed by Van Meter & Van Horn (1975). The results showed that implementing the BKK policy for vocational high school work placements at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency had not been effective. The ineffectiveness of implementing the policy is caused by problems with aspects of the Standards and policy objectives; Resources; Communication between organizations and strengthening activities, Characteristics of implementing agents, Attitudes of implementers, and the economic, social, and political environment that has not been optimally addressed. The ideal strategy to overcome this problem is the Diversification strategy, namely by maximizing the potential strength to overcome or minimize threats in the work placement policy by BKK SMK in Serang Regency.

Keywords: Policy Implementation, Job Market, Job Placement.

A. INTRODUCTION

Employment is an aspect of development (Becker, 2000; Trubek & Mosher, 2003; Mkandawire, 2010). The role of the workforce has an important position and role in regional development following Law No. 13 of 2003 concerning the workforce, which states that workforce development aims to create equal employment opportunities, provide quality labor following regional development needs, empower and utilize the workforce. Optimally and humanely. Article 27, paragraph 2 of the 1945 Constitution states that "every citizen has the right to work and a decent living for humanity." The workforce is an actor in the development process; for the success of a development, an adequate workforce is needed, both in quality and quantity (Chen et al., 2004; Myers & Kellogg, 2022). On the other hand, job creation is

one of the challenges for development strategies and policies in each country. Development in developing countries so far has not been able to create adequate job opportunities for the continuously increasing workforce, thus causing an imbalance between the number of the workforce who need work and the availability of job opportunities which has an impact on increasing the number of unemployed (Grindle, 2004; Lin, 2013; Lawal & Oluwatoyin, 2011).

The problem of unemployment that has occurred in Indonesia so far is due to an imbalance between supply and demand for labor, both in terms of quality and quantity required by the labor market. This imbalance is caused by a lack of information between companies using labor and job seekers (Manning, 2000; Nagib & Ngadi, 2008; Dobbs & Madgavkar, 2014)). Besides, technological sophistication also brings new problems in terms of employment. Human labor played a major role in production activities, but now many of these jobs have been shifted to machines, causing job opportunities to decrease (Townsend et al., 1998; Hu et al., 2021). As a result, the unemployment rate increases because the number of jobs is not proportional to the number of job seekers. After tracing, the number of unemployed is dominated by people with a Vocational High School (SMK) educational background (Pratomo, 2017; Nugraheni, 2021). This is certainly surprising because SMK is a school designed to prepare graduates ready to work. As stated in Law no. 20 of 2003 article 15, vocational education is secondary education that prepares students especially to work in certain fields.

Based on the results of the presentation of data released by the Central Statistics Agency on May 5, 2020, regarding the state of employment in Indonesia, it is known that until February 2020, there was an increase in the number of unemployed by 60 thousand and judging from the level of education, the Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) at the vocational education level was still the lowest. The highest among other levels of education at 8.49 percent. This is, of course, a big question mark why SMK graduates are the biggest contributors to unemployment. When examined more deeply, apparently caused by the SMK curriculum, which is difficult to change. Changes in the curriculum at the vocational level are not in line with the rapid development of the times, so there is a lag. As a result, it is difficult for SMK graduates to find jobs because there is a gap between companies' HR needs to be needed but cannot be met by SMK graduates (CBS, 2020).

One of the efforts to overcome the imbalance of employment problems which resulted in the high unemployment rate is to carry out special job market activities (Habibie et al., 2014). A special job fair is a service for secondary education units, higher education units, and job training institutions that provide workforce placement facilities for alumni. The Special Job Exchange is an activity that aims to bring together job seekers with job seekers to provide information about the availability of positions and an overview of the company in general (Sukardi & Hargiyanto, 2007). By carrying out this activity, it can make it easier for job seekers to communicate directly with various representative employees from companies opening job vacancies (Hardiani, 2017).

In addition to implementing one of the functions of the employment placement service, the function of the Job Exchange is to bring together job seekers and labor users. From this function, it can be seen that the role of the Job Exchange is very important, namely as a

mediator between labor users and workers (graduates) to get jobs (Atmaji, 2019). To realize the objectives of the job fair and carry out its functions optimally, it must be managed professionally by the institution that handles it (Dikti, 2012).

The involvement of BKK in distributing SMK graduates plays a major role in reducing the unemployment rate of SMK graduates. The BKK is expected to be able to find a way out of the causes of difficulties for vocational graduates to find jobs. Empowerment of BKK SMK is one of the functions in school management, namely as part of the development process for implementing BKK SMK activities planned to achieve vocational education goals (Rejeki et al., 2020). The BKK Vocational High School is one component of the implementation of dual system education because it is impossible to carry out a learning process that leads to competence if there is no industrial/business partner, as a work environment where students learn skills and professionalism and work ethic following the demands of the world of work (Susmawati et al., 2021).

Serang Regency is an area within the government area of Banten Province with a fairly high unemployment rate. Data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency of Banten Province shows that Serang Regency has been ranked first as a contributor to the highest unemployment rate in Banten Province for eight consecutive years, namely since 2012, and has only been released from this predicate in 2020, precisely at the time of entering the Covid Pandemic period. -19. The position of Serang Regency regarding the contribution of the unemployment rate in Banten Province can be seen in the table of Open Unemployment (TPT) in Banten Province as follows:

Table 1 Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) in Banten Province

Regency/City	Regency/City Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) in Banten Province (Percent)	
	2018	2019
Pandeglang Regency	8.19	8.67
Lebak Regency	7.57	7.96
Tangerang Regency	9.63	8.92
Serang Regency	12.63	10.58
Tangerang City	7.39	7.14
Cilegon City	9.21	9.64
Serang City	8.10	8.07
South Tangerang City	4.67	4.78
Banten Province	8.47	8.11

Source: BPS Banten Province, 2020

The table above shows the unemployment rate in Serang Regency among other regencies/cities in Banten Province, which tends to be the highest from year to year. According to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) of Banten Province, the

unemployment rate for the 2018 to 2018 period is 2019 for the Serang Regency area was 12.63% in 2018 and 10.58% in 2019. In 2019 the Serang Regency unemployment rate had decreased but increased again in 2020. The high unemployment rate in Serang Regency is still one of the causes of unemployment in Serang Regency. This is a serious problem facing the Serang Regency government at this time. This is ironic because it is one of the districts with a relatively high industrial area.

The local government is tasked with reducing unemployment in its territory to realize the goals of community welfare, and implementing this task is based on Law no. 41 of 2007 is the Office of Manpower and Transmigration, also known as Disnakertrans. The Manpower and Transmigration Office of Serang Regency is an element of implementing technical tasks, and regional autonomy from the center and regions based on the principles of regional autonomy and assistance tasks following the scope of duties and functions and is a regional government institution that has a dominant role and responsibility in alleviating unemployment.

One of the tasks of the Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office is to make it easier for people to get decent jobs to reduce the amount of unemployment that exists; this task is stated in Ministerial Regulation no. 07 of 2008 concerning employment which explains conventionally that the duties and functions of the Manpower and Transmigration Service to the community are so that the community gets jobs and employers in filling job vacancies according to their interests, talents, abilities and explains information about job vacancies, training, counseling, job guidance, and work intermediaries.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Public Administration

Administration in a narrow sense includes activities: taking notes, correspondence, light bookkeeping, typing, activities in compiling information systematically, and taking notes in writing to be documented so that it is easy to find them when they will be used again, either separately. As well as as an inseparable whole and everything technical in nature (clerical work) (Hess & Ledebur, 2011; Fox & Meyer, 1995).

Broadly, the administration is defined by many experts, including Gullick (1937), stating that administration is all things related to the completion of what is to be done, with the achievement of the goals that have been set. While Simon (1995) defines administration as follows: "Administration as the activities of groups cooperating to accomplish common goals," which is defined as administration as group activities that work together to complete common goals. The two expert opinions above show that the element in the implementation of administration is the existence of a goal.

2. Public policy

Winarno (2007) argues that the term policy may be used broadly as in "Indonesia's foreign policy," "Japan's economic policy," and or it may also be used to mean something more specific, for example, if we say the government's policy on debureaucratization and deregulation. However, both Solihin Abdul Wahab and Budi Winarno agree that the term

policy is often used interchangeably with other terms such as program goals, decisions, laws, provisions, standards, proposals, and grand designs (Solichin, 2008).

Dye, as quoted by Islamy (2009), defines public policy as "whatever government chooses to do or not to do" (whatever the government chooses to do or not to do). This definition emphasizes that public policy is about the realization of "action" and is not a mere statement of the will of the government or public officials. In addition, the government's choice not to do something is also a public policy because it has an influence (the same impact as the government's choice to do something (Suharno, 2009).

3. Public Policy Implementation

In Webster's big dictionary, implementing means provides the means for carrying out; and gives practical effect ((Webster in Tangkilisan, 2003). Van Meter and Van Horn then argue that implementation is "Implementation are actions taken either by individuals/officials or government or private groups directed at the achievement of the goals that have been outlined in policy decisions." (Van Meter & Van Horn, 1975), Van Meter and Van Horn's view can be interpreted that implementation is an action by individuals, officials, groups of government or private bodies directed at achieving goals that have been outlined in a particular decision.

4. Framework

The implementation of the Special Job Exchange (BKK) policy in job placement is determined by various factors, including policy standards and targets; Resources; Communication between organizations and strengthening activities, Characteristics of implementing agents, Economic, social and political environment, and Attitudes of implementers. These criteria have relevance to the policy implementation variables proposed by Van Horn & Van Meter (in Agustino, 2008), which measure the success of policy implementation based on the common factors and policy objectives; resources; Communication between organizations and strengthening activities, Characteristics of implementing agents, Economic, social and political environment and Attitudes of implementers. Therefore, methodologically the researcher will use the implementation theory of Van Horn & Van Meter (in Agustino, 2008), which is strengthened or supported by other relevant policy implementation theories.

C. METHOD

The method used in this research is the descriptive research method, where this research focuses on the actual problems as they are when the research is in progress. (Salim & Haidir, 2019). This research is mixed research or mixed-method research or research with combination methods (the concurrent embedded technique was chosen because the analysis process in this study has a dominant approach/primary method, namely qualitative and quantitative methods as secondary methods (insertions) to determine implementation strategies with techniques SWOT analysis The main focus of this research is Policy Implementation, with the sub-focus of research being policy standards and targets, resources, communication between organizations and strengthening activities, characteristics of

implementing agents, attitudes of implementers, and the economic, social and political environment in policy implementation Job Exchange Special job placement at Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency.

D. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of the Employment Exchange Policy for Job Placement at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency

Implementing the Special Job Exchange (BKK) policy in Serang Regency ideally refers to the Regulation of the Minister of Manpower No. 39 of 2016 concerning Work Placement. Based on CHAPTER I General Provisions, Article 1 (Paragraphs 16 and 17) of the Minister of Manpower 39/2016, the Special Job Exchange is a service unit for secondary education units, higher education units, and job training institutions that provide facilitation of Manpower Placement to alumni.

In the Minister of Manpower No. 39 of 2016, it is stated that the recruitment of workers can only be carried out by three elements, namely the company, the Manpower, and Transmigration Service, including the Student Manpower Service Institute, and the Job Training Institute, as well as the Special Job Exchange (BKK).

The Special Job Exchange is overseen by the Ministry of Manpower and the Ministry of Education and Culture. This needs to be monitored so that the BKK can carry out all its duties and responsibilities effectively following applicable regulations so that the BKK can become the right forum for distributing graduates so that the absorption of graduates into the world of work will continue to increase and the unemployment rate will decrease.

BKK reports and accounts for all its activities periodically. Following the Decree of the Director-General of Development and Placement of Domestic Workers, article 12 states that activities carried out by the BKK every month, quarter and year must be reported to the agency responsible for the local workforce sector with a copy to the Minister Director-General of Development and Placement of Domestic Workers. State by using the form. Article 14 explains that if the BKK does not report its activities or does not carry out activities for 6 (six) consecutive months, evaluation and guidance will be carried out. If, after the evaluation and guidance, the BKK has not carried out activities for 12 consecutive months and is strengthened by the absence of a report, the agency responsible for the local workforce sector will revoke the Approval Letter for the Establishment of the BKK.

Following the Regulation of the Minister of Manpower No. 39 of 2016 concerning Work Placement, the Office of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency is tasked with fostering and supervising the implementation of job placements by the Special Jobs Exchange (BKK) in industry. This is stated in CHAPTER I General Provisions, Article 1 (Paragraph 17). The guidance was carried out at the beginning of the formation of the Serang Regency BKK in 2016. Still, the guidance was recognized by the Serang Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office only concerning recruitment tasks, registration of BKK SMK at the Disnakertrans port, not touching the attitude or skills of BKK personnel. . Based on observations, the development of the Vocational Special Employment Exchange, especially

related to governance, skills, and attitudes of BKK personnel to improve the performance of BKK SMKs does not yet exist and has not been regulated in a special policy.

Based on the organizational structure, Serang Regency BKK is under the coordination of the Serang Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office. Still, in its operational work, the BKK unit is within the Vocational High School, an organizational unit under the Banten Province Education and Culture Office. This is the case with BKK personnel.

According to the Cooperation Agreement between the Ministry of Education and Culture and the Ministry of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia No. 076/U/1993 and No. KEP, 215/MEN/1993 in Chapter XI article 10, states that the costs of implementing job market activities in secondary education units are borne by each work unit and in terms of inter-employment services that do not conflict with the provisions of the applicable laws and regulations. To finance the scouting of job fair organizers in secondary education units, the Ministry of Manpower and the Ministry of Education and Culture budget is charged according to the available budget. The BKK budget for carrying out activities is borne by each BKK and from the inter-work service fee, meanwhile for the cost of guiding the BKK organizers, which includes inter-work counseling and guidance activities that are given to supervising teachers, administrative sections, or teachers appointed by the relevant school, from the Ministry of Manpower and the Ministry of Education and Culture.

2. Aspects in the Implementation of the Special Job Market Policy for Job Placement at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency

The ineffectiveness of implementing the BKK policy will be described based on aspects of the study following the theory used as an analytical knife, namely the theory of Policy Implementation by Van Horn and Van Metter (1975) with six aspects of policy implementation consisting of aspects of standard and policy objectives, resources, communication between organizations and strengthening activities, characteristics of implementing agents, attitudes of implementers, and the economic, social and political environment.

a. Policy standards and objectives

Based on the informants' statements above, it can be seen that each party implementing the policy agrees with the standard of the success of the job placement policy for SMK graduates by the BKK, namely the absorption of SMK graduates by industry facilitated by the BKK. In addition to the exposure of the informants, researchers can see that the similarities in each policy standard are that all standards set must be carried out following SOPs (standard operational procedures), but written and measured policymakers have not formulated SOPs. All informants agreed that if the SOP exists, it can be well controlled by each field so that the objectives can be achieved optimally. This condition shows that BKK officers in the field need SOPs in the form of guidance or technical guidelines (technical instructions) to guide and become limitations in the implementation of the duties of each field so that there is no overlap.

b. Resources

In policy implementation, resources are the most important aspect. The resources in question are human resources, budgetary resources, and time resources. This is because implementers

who can succeed or thwart the implementation of a policy must have the quality that follows what is needed or what has been determined by the relevant agency. Likewise, a policy will not work well with budgetary resources if it is not supported by adequate budget availability. Every operational step requires funds for both the implementation of activities and incentives for the officers. The budget is indeed a different obstacle in carrying out the duties of the BKK. This happens because the BKK was formed by the Manpower and Transmigration Office but is in the Vocational School unit, which is under the Provincial Education Office; this dualism is the root of the unclear budget ceiling as well; each agency feels that it does not have the authority to prepare a budget ceiling for BKK activities. This is very sad because the role of the BKK itself is central and very decisive in alleviating educated unemployment, especially SMK graduates, which are the responsibility of local governments.

The study results indicate that each agency related to BKK operations has not yet sat down together to formulate a financing formulation for the implementation of BKK operations. This is also a concern for the Vocational High School unit as a shelter for the BKK. Likewise, not all schools allocate budgets for BKK operations and personnel costs with schools. From the research that has been done, it can be seen that the human resources needed by the Department of Manpower and Transmigration for BKK personnel are quality human resources. Quality human resources will be able to realize the implementation of policies properly and correctly. A lack of unsupported budgetary resources can trigger the low quality of human resources in the Special Job Market. One informant at the Manpower and Transmigration Office stated that "the lack of quality human resources is due to the absence of special training for BKK personnel because there is no budget to carry out these activities."

c. Communication between organizations

There are differences in the application of communication carried out by the informants. The Manpower and Transmigration Office stated that they had tried and taken steps to communicate with the agencies related to the work placement by the BKK. However, the school and industry consider that these efforts have not been delivered optimally, with obstacles and policy outputs still being found that are not following the policy objectives. At the Office of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency, the Office's communication process to institutions related to job placement by the Special Job Exchange has been carried out. Still, the study results also show that elements other than the Service feel that the communication between the Service and Industry, Schools, and BKK Personnel itself is still not optimal.

This is caused by the less structured delivery of information, which is one of the inhibiting factors in communication. As well as in, the delivery of information must be conveyed clearly and consistently. Following the theory put forward by Edward that three things affect the success or badness of communication, namely, transmission, clarity, and consistency. Communication between organizations is also very necessary to ensure the synchronization between the needs of the industry, the provision of suitable graduates, and the distribution of vocational workers. The informants also stated this in the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) question and answer forum; all elements stated that there was still synchrony between the SMK graduates produced and the industry's need for the workforce.

d. Characteristics of implementing agents

In policy implementation, to achieve maximum success, one must know the characteristics of the implementing agent, including the bureaucratic structure, norms, and patterns of relationships that occur in the bureaucracy, all of which will affect the implementation of a predetermined policy program. The characteristics of implementing agents include bureaucratic structures, norms, and patterns of relationships that occur in the bureaucracy, all of which will affect the implementation of a predetermined policy program.

The study results illustrate that the pattern of relationships between Manpower and Transmigration Offices and organizations related to the job placement of SMK graduates is still not said to be effective. Constraints that occur in the pattern of relationships can be one of the causes of the ineffective implementation of work placement policies by BKK Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency.

e. The attitude of implementers (Disposition)

The fifth study aspect is the disposition or attitude of the implementer. According to Edward (1982), a disposition in implementation and characteristics and attitudes possessed by policy implementers such as commitment and honesty. A good implementer must have a good disposition, so he will be able to implement good policies as desired and determined by policymakers. The attitude or disposition of the implementer is divided into three things: The response of the implementer to policies related to the implementer's policy to implement public policy; conditions, namely understanding of the policies that have been set; and the intensity of the disposition of the implementer. These three things are closely related to each other. The willingness of employees to implement policies is very important. An employee's agreement with the policy will encourage employees to know and understand the policy and how to apply the policy to its portion.

Informants gave various responses related to the job placement policy. Some were optimistic about the existence of the BKK policy in Permenaker 39 of 2016; others were pessimistic because they considered this policy to be nothing more than ceremonial without continuous follow-up. The disposition of the implementers in the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency is good. This policy regarding work placement by the BKK was well received by BKK personnel and other elements involved in its implementation. Based on the study results, the attitude of policy implementers (disposition) in responding to the BKK policy in vocational work placements in Serang Regency was influenced by various experiences in the institution.

f. The economic, social and political environment

Informant statements related to environmental elements are entirely related to environmental intervention in the industrial recruitment process, including extortion and intervention by environmental officials. This is a concern for the performance of the BKK in the placement of vocational graduates. Many schools cannot recruit independently in schools because they are opposed by the environment, in this case, the village apparatus in power. Of course, this hinders the work and duties of the BKK to distribute graduates to the industry without any fees.

From the research above, it can be seen that the environment greatly influences the success of policy implementation. The socio-political and cultural environment in the city of Serang is

considered less supportive of the implementation of policies by the informants. One of the indications is the rampant culture of brokering, thuggery, intimidation of local officials, political intervention in recruitment, and even regional culture that is still attached to graduates, which hinders job placement in the industry by the BKK.

3. Strategy for the Implementation of Special Job Exchange Policies for Job Placement at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency

Implementing the Employment Exchange Policy for Job Placement at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency can be carried out using an analytical approach of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats or with the term SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, and Treats).

Table 2 SWOT analysis table

No	SWOT	Description
1	Strength	Industrial potential in Serang Regency is very high, The number of SMK in Serang Regency is high, SMK development is a government priority program Formation of the BKK Unit at SMK Serang Regency is high
2	Weakness	The bureaucratic structure is still convoluted, There is no specific regulation governing BKK operations at the district level. The infrastructure of many school units is inadequate The construction of the new SMK unit does not meet the standards.
3	Opportunities	Geographically, Serang Regency is very close to the provincial capital, with easy access SMK development program is a government priority (Kepres Vocational Revitalization) The number of industries facilitates BKK cooperation Job placement opportunities are quite high
4	Treats	Student parent's feudal culture The culture of thuggery in the work placement process is still thick The graduate mindset to work close to home (don't want to be far) Apparatus intervention on industry recruitment mechanisms

Source: Processed by researchers (2022)

Internal strategy factor analysis or IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary) and external strategic factor analysis or EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary) are carried out by assigning weights and ratings to each strategic factor.

Table 3 Analysis of Internal Factors

Internal Strategy Factors	Tk. Sig	Weight	Rating	Score
Strength				
Industrial potential in Serang Regency is very high,	3	0.3	4	1.2
The number of SMK in Serang City is high	3	0.3	4	1.2
SMK development is a government priority program	2	0.2	3	0.6
The formation of the BKK Unit at SMK Serang Regency is high	2	0.2	3	0.6
TOTAL	10	1		3.6
Weakness				
The bureaucratic structure is still convoluted	2	0.2	2	0.4
There is no specific regulation governing BKK operations at the district level	2	0.2	2.5	0.6
The infrastructure of many school units is inadequate	3	0.3	2	0.7
The construction of the new SMK unit does not meet the standards	2	0.2	2	0.4
TOTAL				2.1
GRAND TOTAL				5.7

Source: Processed by researchers (2022)

Table 4 Analysis of External Factors

External Strategy Factors	Sig	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunity				
Geographically, Serang Regency is very close to the provincial capital, with easy access	3	0.3	2	0.6
SMK development program is a government priority (Kepres Vocational Revitalization)	3	0.3	2.5	0.75
The number of industries facilitates BKK cooperation	2	0.2	2	0.4
Job placement opportunities are quite high	2	0.2	2	0.4
TOTAL	10	1		2.15
Threat				
Student parent's feudal culture	3	0.3	4	1.1
The culture of thuggery in the work placement process is still thick	3	0.3	4	1.1
The graduate mindset to work close to home (don't want to be far)	3	0.3	3	0.8
Apparatus intervention on industry recruitment mechanisms	2	0.2	3	0.5
TOTAL	11	1		3.5
GRAND TOTAL				5.65

Source: Processed by researchers (2022)

The table above shows that obtaining a strength score is greater than a weakness. Meanwhile, the score for threats is greater for external factors than for opportunities.

1. Strength – Weakness = 3.6 – 2.1 = 1.5
2. Opportunities – Threats = 2.15 – 3.6 = -1.45

The results of the previous calculations are then used as a reference for the formation of a SWOT analysis to see the potential position of the BKK policy on job placement at the Manpower and Transmigration Office, as outlined in the following diagram:

Figure 1 SWOT Analysis Diagram of the Strategy for Implementing the BKK Policy at the Manpower and Transmigration Office of Serang Regency

Strategy Implementation of the Special Job Exchange Policy for Job Placement at the Manpower and Transmigration Office of Serang Regency, according to the results of qualitative research essence it has not been fully implemented, so it has not been able to realize the policy goal, namely the high absorption of SMK graduates to minimize unemployment in Serang Regency, even though the policy is The Special Job Market is very important and has a very big role.

The diversification strategy that can be implemented by the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency to maximize the BKK policy in the placement of vocational students is as follows:

1. Establish a policy of strengthening cooperation with the Provincial Education Office for supervision and control
2. Maximizing the potential for the quantity of BKK to gain cooperation with as many industries as possible. The high number of BKK must guarantee the MoU with a high industry as well. This can be realized by providing guidance and training to BKK units to be reliable in attracting cooperation.

3. Maximizing the quality of graduates is carried out by linking and matching learning in vocational schools with industrial needs. This will increase the competitiveness of vocational high school graduates. BKK must be actively involved in improving the quality of SMK graduates.

E. CONCLUSION

Based on the study results, it can be seen that the BKK policy on job placement at Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency has not been implemented effectively. This is indicated by the high unemployment rate for Serang Regency Vocational Schools. Aspects that determine the successful implementation of the BKK policy on job placements at Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency are policy standards and objectives, resources, communication between organizations and strengthening activities, characteristics of implementing agents, attitudes of implementers, and the economic, social and political environment. The aspect that is very urgent and gets more attention is the environmental aspect, especially related to the mindset of students and parents who are influenced by a local culture that is not yet open and environmental interventions related to employment by industry. Using SWOT analysis, effective policy implementation strategies in job placement were carried out by the Vocational High School BKK, namely the Diversification strategy.

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